

Toward the remote monitoring of armed conflicts: Supplementary Table 1

Authors	Year	Type of research	Type of Conflict Events	Conflict Events	Scope	Region (UN Geoscheme)	Technique type	Satellite image cluster ¹	Optical or SAR
Aung	2021	Conflict Study	Structural damage, environmental damage	Burned land, demolition of human settlements	Regional	South-eastern Asia	AI-based supervised	Clusters 1 and 3	Optical
Bolorani et al.	2021	Technical	Structural damage	Damaged and destroyed urban areas	City/cities	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 3	SAR
Braun	2018	Technical	Structural damage	Damaged and destroyed buildings	City/cities	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 3	SAR
Checchi et al.	2013	Technical	Displacement	Displaced populations	Local	Southern Asia, Middle Africa, Eastern Africa, Caribbean	Visual analysis	Cluster 1	Optical
Coscieme et al.	2017	Conflict Study	Other (proxy)	Occurrence and intensity of conflicts	International	Global	Traditional detection	Cluster 4	Optical
Fakhri and Gkanatsios	2021	Technical	Structural damage	Damaged and destroyed buildings, loss of settlement	City/cities	Western Asia	AI-based supervised	Cluster 3	Both
Friedrich and Van Den Hoek	2020	Technical	Displacement	Refugee settlements	Local	Eastern Africa	AI-based unsupervised	Cluster 3	Optical
Ghorbanzadeh et al.	2018	Technical	Displacement	Tents and buildings in refugee settlements	Local	Middle Africa	AI-based supervised	Cluster 1	Optical
Ghorbanzadeh et al.	2021	Technical	Displacement	Dwellings in a refugee camp	Local	Middle Africa	AI-based supervised	Cluster 1	Optical
Jenerowicz et al.	2019	Technical	Displacement	IDP settlements, refugee camps	Local	Northern Africa, Eastern Africa	Traditional detection	Cluster 1	Optical
Jiang et al.	2017	Conflict Study	Decrease in economic activities, structural damage (proxy)	Damage of urban infrastructure, decrease in oil exploration	National	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 4	Optical
Kahraman et al.	2016	Technical	Structural damage	Damaged buildings	Local	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 1	Optical
Knoth and Pebesma	2017	Technical	Structural damage	Destructed dwellings	Local	Northern Africa	Traditional detection	Cluster 1	Optical
Knoth et al.	2018	Technical	Structural damage	Destroyed dwelling structures	Local	Northern Africa	Traditional detection	Cluster 1	Optical
Levin et al.	2018	Technical	Structural damage (proxy)	Damaged infrastructure	International	Northern Africa, Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 4	Optical
Levin et al.	2019	Conflict Study	Structural damage (proxy), environmental damage (proxy)	Infrastructure damage, fires	International	Northern Africa, Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 4	Optical

¹ Cluster 1: commercial, archival tasked, high-spatial resolution images. Cluster 2: commercial, regular revisiting cycle, high-spatial resolution images. Cluster 3: freely available, regular revisiting cycle, moderate-spatial resolution images. Cluster 4: freely available, regular revising cycle, low-spatial resolution images.

Li and Li	2014	Technical	Displacement (proxy)	IDP population	National	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 4	Optical
Li et al.	2013	Technical	Other (proxy)	Onset of conflict, ceasefires	International	Global	Traditional detection	Cluster 4	Optical
Li et al.	2017	Technical	Structural damage (proxy)	Damage and reconstruction of electricity supply	national	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 4	Optical
Li et al.	2018	Conflict Study	Structural damage (proxy)	Damaged electric supply	National	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 4	Optical
Li et al.	2015	Conflict Study	Other (proxy)	Lack of access to electricity supply	Regional	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 4	Optical
Lubin and Saleem	2019	Technical	Structural damage	Damaged buildings	City/cities	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 3	Optical
Marx	2016	Technical	Structural damage	Destroyed urban buildings	City/cities	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 3	Optical
Marx and Loboda	2013	Technical	Structural damage	Destroyed villages	Regional	Northern Africa	Traditional detection	Cluster 3	Optical
Marx et al.	2019	Technical	Structural damage	Burned and burning villages	Local	South-eastern Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 2	Optical
Mueller et al.	2021	Technical	Structural damage	Destroyed buildings	City/cities	Western Asia	AI-based supervised	Clusters 1 and/or 2	Optical
Pech and Lakes	2017	Technical	Displacement	Urban expansion	City/cities	Middle Africa	Visual analysis	Cluster 3	Optical
Redmond	2021	Technical	Structural damage	Destroyed settlements and dwellings	Regional	South-eastern Asia	AI-based supervised	Cluster 3	Optical
Ren et al.	2020	Technical	Displacement, structural damage, environmental damage	Fire, camp construction, razing of villages	Regional	South-eastern Asia	Traditional detection	Clusters 3 and 4	Both
Shah et al.	2020	Technical	Structural damage (proxy)	Damage to electricity grids	City/cities	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 4	Optical
Spröhnle et al.	2014	Technical	Displacement	IDP settlements	Local	Eastern Africa	Traditional detection	Cluster 1	Optical
Spröhnle et al.	2017	Technical	Displacement	Different dwelling types in a refugee camp	Local	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 1	Both
Tapete and Cigna	2016	Technical	Kinetic activity, structural damage	Military blockage, trenches, excavations, embankments, damaged buildings	City/cities	Western Asia	Traditional detection	Clusters 1 and 3	SAR
Tiede et al.	2017	Technical	Displacement	Refugee camps	Local	Eastern Africa, Northern Africa, Middle Africa	Traditional detection	Cluster 1	Optical
Wang et al.	2015	Technical	Displacement	Tents in IDP and refugee camps	Local	South-eastern Asia, Western Asia	Traditional detection	Cluster 1	Optical

Table S1: main attributes of studies included in the review section. Own categorization.